

OPTIMIZING PREGRAVIDARNOY PODGOTOVKI GINSCHIN WITH CHRONIC HYPOPLASTIC ENDOMETRITOM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896993>

Relevance: Significantly better outcomes were seen when patients were younger than 35 years or when the number of oocytes retrieved was >5 or the number of embryos transferred was 3 or more. The authors concluded that patients should be offered an embryo cryopreservation program if the TE was <7 mm on the day of oocyte retrieval and the number of embryos was ≥ 3 [14]. Although this study supports the idea that TE <7 mm reduces the chance of pregnancy, results based on stratification by age, oocyte number, and embryos transferred suggest that TE is not the only determinant of outcome.

Purpose of the study: A meta-analysis describes a diametrically opposite view. (2014), included 1170 patients enrolled in ART programs. According to the authors, TE in ART protocols cannot be used as a marker to cancel the embryo transfer protocol, incl. and cryopreserved [33].

Study materials: The frequency of endometrium (≤ 7 mm) was low and was 2.4% (260 of 10,724). However, there was also a trend toward lower CNB and live birth rates in these women (odds ratio [OR] = 0.38; 95% confidence interval [CI] - 0.09–1.5), as TE The odds of clinical pregnancy with ≤ 7 mm were significantly lower compared with >7 mm (23.3 vs 48.1% or OR=0.42; 95% CI - 0.27-0.67). Positive predictive value for clinical pregnancy was 77%, negative - 48%. We can conclude from this review: TE can predict our probability, but cannot be a factor in predicting pregnancy [33].

Observed results: Meanwhile, it should be noted that some authors describe the negative effects of controlled ovarian stimulation on ER and recommend cryopreservation of embryos to improve implantation, followed by cycles of hormone replacement therapy [14].

Based on the above, it was interesting to investigate the importance of TE for CCNB and the results of embryo cryopreserved transfer cycles. For example, in the studies of T. El-Touxy et al. (2008) found that TE = 9–14 mm measured on the day of initiation of progesterone support was associated with higher implantation and CNNB compared with TE = 7–8 mm [13].

Also interesting are the results of E. Dix and JH Check (2010), who studied pregnancy rates in patients with TE<6 mm [37] in a retrospective analysis. Only 3 of 35 patients became pregnant and 2 gave birth. The pregnancy rate in the study cohort was 8.5%.

However, the results of a recent study by the same group of researchers [38] comparing CNNB between new and cryoprotocols with TE<6 mm were pessimistic; CNNB TE = 4-5 mm. compared with the cryoprotocol, the new protocol was 10.6 versus 27.2% (p = 0.079).

Conclusions: Egg donation (oocyte donation) cycles are ideal for measuring the independent effect of TE as a parameter of endometrial receptivity, as there is less variability in embryo quality. In connection with the above, the data of L. Dain et al. (2013), who studied the effect of TE on reproductive outcome in oocyte donation cycles using 6.0 and 8.2 mm as endpoints for inclusion in the group with thin endometrial syndrome [27]. Statistically significant differences in CNNB (29.6 vs. 30.0%) and live birth rate (16.7 vs. 23.6%) in women with TE>6 mm vs. TE<6 mm there was no. However, the researchers noted that the group with a TE no greater than 8.2 mm had a higher percentage of live births than those with a "thinner" endometrium. Perhaps the "thin" endometrium does not support the development of pregnancy after implantation, which leads to more miscarriages due to intrauterine death of the fetus.

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